

EXA4MIND

RAFFLE

WIN WITH THE EXA4MIND PROJECT

Would you like to win one of
3 external hard drives?

WHEN?

MONDAY AT 7 PM

TUESDAY AND WEDNESDAY AT 1 PM

Funded by
the European Union